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D3.1 Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v1

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
EC	European Commission
ETL	Extract, Transform and Load process
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
UI	User Interface
VPME	Virtual Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Abstract

This deliverable is a demonstrator of the Data Management component in AI4PublicPolicy developed in the context of work package 3, AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies. This component was developed in the context of task 3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets. The Data Management component is used for loading the datasets into the AI4PublicPolicy platform. This data will be exploited by the AI analysis tools in AI4PublicPolicy. The data is stored according to the data model developed in the project based on the datasets from the different pilots. The Data Management component software is able to deal with data-at-rest and streaming data in different format and from different data sources that can be configured. The Data Management can deal with Big Data running in a distributed environment.

Executive summary

This deliverable is a demonstrator of the Data Management component in AI4PublicPolicy developed in the context of work package 3, AI-based Reusable and Interoperable Policies. This component was developed in the context of task 3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets. The Data Management component is used for loading the datasets into the AI4PublicPolicy platform. This data will be exploited by the AI analysis tools in AI4PublicPolicy. The data is stored according to the data model developed in the project based on the datasets from the different pilots. The Data Management component software is able to deal with data-at-rest and streaming data in different format and from different data sources that can be configured. The Data Management can deal with Big Data running in a distributed environment.

The Data Management component software can be deployed as a standalone component independent of the rest of the platform, the VPME, behaving as an ETL for any dataset that needs to be stored in a datastore with different formats. This component can be downloaded as a Docker image or as an application for the Linux environment. The former is easier to use and is configured to run as a centralized single node component. The latter allows the distribution of the ETL to cope with Big Data.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding, and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Objective of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the first version of the software for the Collection and Management of Datasets developed at this phase of the project in the context of task T3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets. This software is in charge of collecting and storing the datasets from the different pilots in AI4PublicPolicy datastore. The deliverable describes

the architecture of the component, its subcomponents, how it is used and how the software is distributed.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the Data Management component in the context of the AI4PublicPolicy project and presents its architecture. The next sections are devoted to the description of the main subcomponents of the Data Management (Sections 3, 4 and 5). Section 6 describes how the Data Management software can be deployed. Finally, Section 7 concludes the deliverable and points out future work concerning the task T3.1 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets.

2 Collection and Management of Public Policy Datasets

The Data Management component at the bottom of Figure 2 is in charge of the collection and management of the datasets from different stakeholders in the AI4PublicPolicy. The dataset management component loads and stores the data to be analyzed by the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME). Data can be collected from diverse data source types and in different formats including data at-rest and streaming data.

Figure 2: AI4PublicPolicy main components

The Data Management component must consider different data sources providing data in different formats, and with different schemas to be useful for a wide range of applications. It also considers data sources that provide data-at-rest (files with the data) and streaming data (e.g., data that is not stored and comes directly from the source in a continuous manner). The data is then stored in a SQL database for further processing. This type of datastore can be integrated with tools for semantic processing like *Apache Jena* [1]. An initial data model has been developed based on the datasets provided by the pilots (more than 30 different datasets).

2.1 Data Management Architecture

The Data Management component is made of a set of sub-components shown in Figure 3. It provides a REST API to connect to. The Data Collector component manages the request and starts the data collection process. This process downloads the data (Data Retrieval component) which may have different formats (CSV, JSON, GeoJSON...) and stores it in the datastore (Data Injector). These data can be later analysed by the VPME.

Figure 3: Management of Datasets Component Internal Architecture

2.2 Data Collector

The Data Management component is accessed through a web service that currently is running at <http://138.100.12.242:54745/>. Figure 4 shows the Swagger UI with the API of the Data Collector.

Figure 4: Collection and Management of Datasets component interface

The data collector request has as parameter a JSON object with three fields: *endpoint*, *sourceType*, and *dataSetSchemaJSON*. The *endpoint* indicates the endpoint from where the dataset is reachable to be downloaded. The *sourceType* describes the format of data in the dataset (JSON, CSV..), if it is static data or *streaming*, if it is data streaming. The *dataSetSchemaJSON* provides an endpoint where the JSON with the schema of the dataset is provided. Figure 5 shows an example of the JSON object with the request for the collection of a dataset that is available in JSON format at <http://opendata-cml.gart.pt/measurements/METEMP0001?startDate=202106240000&endDate=202106250000> and whose dataset schema is defined by a JSON object available at <https://dl.lsdupm.ovh/Projects/AI4PP/schemas/CitySensorsHistoricalData.json>.

```
{
  "endpoint": "http://opendata-cml.gart.pt/measurements/METEMP0001?startDate=202106240000&endDate=202106250000",
  "sourceType": "json",
  "dataSetSchemaJSON": "https://dl.lsdupm.ovh/Projects/AI4PP/schemas/CitySensorsHistoricalData.json"
}
```

Figure 5: Data Collector JSON example

When the Data Collector receives a request, it starts the data retrieval and data injector flow. First the Data Collector identifies the table of the AI4PublicPolicy datastore in which the data is going to be stored. This table is chosen matching the provided schema of the dataset with the ones of the tables in the AI4PublicPolicy datastore. Then, the Data Retrieval component downloads the dataset if the source type is not streaming and invokes the Data Injector component to store the data.

2.3 Data Retrieval

The Data Retrieval gets the actual dataset and schema from different data sources available in the form of a file, database, or streaming data and in different formats. If the dataset is a file (not streaming data), the Data Retrieval component downloads the corresponding file and stores it temporarily until it is loaded into the datastore. If the format is streaming, the schema includes the endpoint from where the data is going to be read which will be used by the Data Injector component. The Data Retrieval component is implemented in Python.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show a sample file dataset and its schema, respectively. The file represents the historical values of a temperature sensor. The schema of this dataset consists of the sensor identifier, the temporal basis of the measurement, the date of the measurement, the value of the sensor and the units of the value.

```

1 [{"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106250000","value":22.5,"unit":"°C"},
2 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106242300","value":23,"unit":"°C"},
3 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106242200","value":23.7,"unit":"°C"},
4 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106242100","value":25,"unit":"°C"},
5 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106242000","value":26.2,"unit":"°C"},
6 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241900","value":27.2,"unit":"°C"},
7 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241800","value":28.5,"unit":"°C"},
8 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241700","value":29.5,"unit":"°C"},
9 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241600","value":31.6,"unit":"°C"},
10 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241500","value":31.1,"unit":"°C"},
11 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241400","value":30.4,"unit":"°C"},
12 {"id":"METEMP0001","avg":"1h","date":"202106241300","value":28.7,"unit":"°C"},

```

Figure 6: CitySensorsHistoricalData dataset example

```

1 {"fields":
2   [{"description": "Identification of the parameters and sensor", "name": "id", "type": "STRING", "mode": "REQUIRED"},
3   {"description": "Temporal basis of the measurement/record", "name": "avg", "type": "STRING", "mode": "REQUIRED"},
4   {"description": "date of the record", "name": "date", "type": "DATETIME", "mode": "REQUIRED"},
5   {"description": "parameter value registered by the sensor", "name": "value", "type": "NUMERIC", "mode": "REQUIRED"},
6   {"description": "units of the record/measurement", "name": "unit", "type": "STRING", "mode": "REQUIRED"}
7 ]
8 }

```

Figure 7: CitySensorsHistoricalData dataset schema

2.4 Data Injector

The Data Injector component reads the file with the dataset and its schema downloaded by the Data Retrieval component and stores the dataset into the AI4PublicPolicy datastore. The Data Injector component is implemented in JAVA programming language using the *Apache Beam* [2] framework (Figure 8) and *Apache Flink* [3] as runner. *Apache Beam* provides a unified model for the definition of batch and streaming processing pipelines or model. Pipelines can be defined in JAVA, Python or Go, which are executed by a runner, for instance *Spark* [4], *Flink*, *Samza* [5], and *Google Cloud Dataflow* [6] among others.

Figure 8: Apache Beam Model

The Beam Models are based on the principle of pipelines. A pipeline encapsulates the data processing task: the reading input data, transforming the data and writing the output data. It is possible to define the input data schema through a schema JSON object whose fields are defined in the *BigQuery* format [7]. Figure 7 presents an example of the JSON object. The data can be consumed and written from/to different source types [8], like File-based, FileSystem (e.g., Hadoop Distributed File System, Google Cloud Storage, Local File System and Amazon S3), messaging systems (e.g., Kinesis, Apache Kafka, MQTT and RabbitMQ among others) and databases (*Apache Cassandra*, *Google Cloud Bigtable*, *MongoDB*, *JDBC* and *Redis* among others), moreover other I/O formats are being developed. Figure 9 shows all available I/O formats *Apache Beam* can deal with.

Figure 9: Apache Beam Input and Output formats and sources

The pipeline data source is configured with the location of the dataset in the storage and the dataset JSON schema object. Once the *data source* is configured, the data is read in the pipeline and transformed to be stored in the AI4PublicPolicy datastore. For instance, the *datetime* field in the dataset in Figure 6 uses the format *yyyyMMddhhmm*, being *yyyy* the year, *MM* the month, *dd* the day, *hh* the hour from 0 to 23, and *mm* the minutes. The *DATETIME* field in BigQuery format uses a different format, *YYYY-[M]M-[D]D[(|T)[H]H:[M]M:[S]S[.F]*. The *Transform fields* operator in the pipeline will do this transformation (Figure 11). Then, the data is stored in a datastore (*JDBC IO Write Output Data*), in this case a MySQL database. Figure 10 shows how the MySQL injector is configured in the pipeline.

```

.apply(JdbcIO.<Row>write()
    .withDataSourceConfiguration(JdbcIO.DataSourceConfiguration.create(
        "com.mysql.jdbc.Driver", "jdbc:mysql://" + options.getDBIP() + ":3306/ai4pp")
        .withUsername(options.getUser())
        .withPassword(options.getPassword())
        .withStatement(options.getDBStatement())
        .withBatchSize(options.getBatchSize())
        .withPreparedStatementSetter(new JdbcIO.PreparedStatementSetter<Row>() {
            public void setParameters(Row elements, PreparedStatement query)
                throws SQLException {
                int i=1;
                for (Object element : elements.getValues()) {
                    query.setObject(i++, element);
                }
            }
        })
    );

```

Figure 10: JDBCIO transform example

Figure 11: Data Injector Beam Pipeline

D3.1 Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v1

The AI4PublicPolicy database has been previously designed and created taking into account the datasets identified by the pilots and documented in deliverable D2.3 Datasets and Data Policies Models. The corresponding data model is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: AI4PublicPolicy Datasets Data Model

The progress of injecting data can be monitored using the *Flink* GUI (Figure 13). Once the *Flink* job completes, the data is available in the database, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 13: CitySensorsHistoricalData Flink job execution

D3.1 Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v1

```
mysql> select * from CitySensorsHistoricalData;
```

id	avg	date	value	unit
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 00:00:00	17.7	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 01:00:00	17.2	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 02:00:00	16.8	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 03:00:00	17.2	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 04:00:00	16.6	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 05:00:00	16.5	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 06:00:00	17.9	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 07:00:00	20.7	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 08:00:00	22.4	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 09:00:00	24.6	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 10:00:00	26.2	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 11:00:00	26.7	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 12:00:00	27.6	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 13:00:00	28.7	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 14:00:00	30.4	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 15:00:00	31.1	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 16:00:00	31.6	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 17:00:00	29.5	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 18:00:00	28.5	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 19:00:00	27.2	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 20:00:00	26.2	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 21:00:00	25.0	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 22:00:00	23.7	°C
METEMP0001	1h	2021-06-24 23:00:00	23.0	°C

24 rows in set (0.00 sec)

Figure 14: CitySensorsHistoricalData in the AI4PublicPolicy DataStore

3 Data Management Software Distribution

The Data Management component can be deployed through the Linux distribution zip file or as Docker image. The Data Management component can be deployed as an independent component of the VPME. This component requires a datastore to store the data.

3.1 Linux Distribution

The Data Management component runs on Linux environments. It requires Java 1.8.x or a higher version. The distribution zip file is available at <https://dl.lsdupm.ovh/Projects/AI4PP/ai4pp-dataCollector-1.0.0.zip>.

Configuration

The `conf/configParams.sh` file must be updated with the IP address where the service will be available, the location of the datastore and other information for configuring the database.

- `DATA_COLLECTOR_HOST` and `DATA_COLLECTOR_PORT` corresponds to the IP and port where the webservice will be running.
- `DB_IP` and `DB_PORT` indicates where the database is running.
- `DB_NAME` configures the name of the database.
- `DB_USER` and `DB_PASS` gives access to the database.

Execution modes

The Data Management component can run in a single node (standalone version) or in a distributed set-up to deal with high amounts of data. The current distribution of the Data Management component uses *Flink* as runner for the Data Injector. *Flink* can run as a standalone component in the same node where the rest of the Data Management components will run. *Flink* can also be deployed in a distributed mode where the *Flink TaskManager* services are executed at different nodes in a cluster for distributing the load among them.

Starting in standalone mode

The next commands show how to start and stop the Data Management component in standalone mode:

```
#The Data Management distribution is unzipped. The commands are
executed in the folder where the distribution is unzipped

#1. Installation
#Checks if the required Flink distribution is in the folder configured
in the conf/configParams.sh file. If not, it downloads the required
version from the Flink repository.
#It configures the database connection parameters
$ cd bin; ./install_data_collector.sh

#2. Start the Data Management
$ ./start_data_collector.sh
```

Starting in distributed mode

The distributed mode runs *Flink* in a distributed set-up. *Flink* distribution must be configured to run in distributed mode following *Flink* documentation in [9]. Once *Flink* is configured, the service is started and stopped as in the standalone mode.

3.2 Data Management Docker Distribution

The Docker image of the Data Management component allows to work with it in any node where Docker is installed. All the files required to generate the docker image are available <https://dl.isdupm.ovh/Projects/AI4PP/ai4pp-dataCollector-1.0.0-docker.zip>

The decompressed file has this structure:

- ai4pp-dataCollector-1.0.0.zip
- configParams.sh
- docker-compose.yml
- Dockerfile
- README.md

```
#Create the Docker image
$ docker build -t ai4pp-collector .

#Run the Data Management

$ docker stack deploy --compose-file docker-compose.yml collector

#Stop the Data Management
$ docker stack rm collector
```

4 Conclusions

This deliverable is a demonstrator deliverable that presents an overview of Data Management component, its architecture and how it can be used and deployed. Some examples from its usage have been presented. The software is available to be downloaded and used as an application running under a Linux environment or a Docker image.

A second updated version of this deliverable is foreseen in month M18. That version will consider more datasets and possibly in different formats and from different data sources. Based on the pilots' experience during this period and their feedback, new features may be supported in the second version of the Data Management software.

5 References

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